

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF 2-AMINO-1, 3, 4- OXODIAZOLE DERIVATIVES

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Abstract:

A simple protocol for the synthesis of 2-amino-1, 3, 4-oxadiazole derivatives using iodoacetic acid as a cyclodesulfurization agent. This method is also applicable to the synthesis of various substituted 2-amino-1, 3, 4-oxadiazole derivatives such as 5-(2-bromophenyl)-N-phenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-amine. The synthesized methodology was simple and hazardless, it's giving good yield.

Key Words: Methyl 2-Bromobenzoate, Methyl 2-Hydroxybenzoate, Thiophosgene, Aryl Isothiocyanate, Hydrazine Hydrate & Iodoacetic Acid

1. Introduction:

1, 3, 4-Oxadiazoles have found extensive use as pharmacophores due to their metabolic property. 2-amino-1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles have wide range of biological activities such as antimicrobial agents, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, muscle relaxants and mitotic [1]. Some 2,5-diaryl substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles act as platelet aggregators [2], antibacterial [3], insecticidal [4], herbicidal/fungicidal [5] and hypotension [6]. Synthesis of 1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles involves cyclodesulfurization of thiosemicarbazide [7], isoselenocyanates via cyclodeselenization [8], using polymer-supported reagents [9], phosphonium mediated reagents [10], hypervalent Iodine mediated method [11]. The reported method frequently requires heating and long reaction time, furthermore formation of urea side product can pose significant challenges during purification. We recognized that this process could be considerably simplified by using iodoacetic acid as a cyclodesulfurization agent and using ethanol solvent to provide desired product at 65°C, 3 hours without formation of side product with high yields.

2. Experimental Section:

A. Methods and Materials: The chemicals of substituted aryl esters, thiophosgene, substituted anilines, ethanol and dichloromethane were obtained from Avra and Sigma Aldrich. Silica gel (TLC and Column grade) were purchased from Merck. The NMR spectra of the compounds have been recorded on Bruker AV400 spectrometer operating at 400 MHz for recording ¹H NMR spectra in DMSO as solvent using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra have been recorded on SHIMADZU spectrometer using chemical ionization technique.

B. Synthesis:

1. General Preparation of Substituted Benzohydrazide Compounds (2a-b)

General Procedure:

To a solution of substituted aryl ester (1a-b) (5g, 0.0239mmol, 1eq), and hydrazine hydrate (5.81g, 0.116mmol, 5eq) in 50 ml of anhydrous ethanol was added at room temperature. The reaction mixture was heated at 80°C and stirred for 5hrs. TLC was indicated absence of starting materials. The residue was diluted with water and then extracted with dichloro methane (300mlX3). The combined organic layer washed with brine solution and dried with sodium sulphate and filtered, concentrated to afford compound (2a-b) as a white colour powder. The crude product was taken next step without further purification.

2. General Preparation of Substituted Phenylthiosemicarbazide Compounds (3a-b)

General Procedure:

To a solution of compounds (2a-b) (2g, 0.0092mmol, 1eq) and phenyl isothiocyanate (1.25g, 0.0092mmol, 1eq) in 20 ml of dichloromethane was added at 0°C. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2hrs at room temperature. TLC was indicated absence of starting materials. The residue was diluted with water and then extracted with dichloro methane (30ml*3times). The combined organic layer washed with brine solution and dried with sodium sulphate and filtered, concentrated to afford compound (3a-b) as a light brown colour powder. The crude product was taken next step without further purification.

3. General Preparation of Substituted n-phenyl-1, 3, 4-Oxadiazol-2-Amine compounds (4a-b)

General Procedure:

Compounds (3a-b) (0.5g, 0.00142mmol, 1eq) dissolved in 20mL ethanol. To this mixture iodoacetic acid (0.26g, 0.00142mmol, 1eq) was added at 0°C. This reaction mixture heated for 3hrs at 65°C. TLC was indicated absence of starting materials. The residue was diluted with water and then extracted with dichloro methane (30ml*3times). The combined organic layer washed with brine solution and dried with sodium sulphate and filtered, concentrated to afford product as dirty white colour.

Scheme: Synthetic route of substituted 2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

3. Results and Discussion:

Spectral details of 2-bromobenzohydrazide(2a)

Mass (m/z): Calculated M.W: 215.25, Observed M.W: 218.0 (M+3)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO -d₆): δ = 9.5(-NH, s, 1H), 4.48(-NH₂, S, 1H), Ar(C-H) = 7.34(m, 2H), 7.40-7.44(d, 1H), 7.64-7.66x(d, 1H)

Spectral details of 2-hydroxybenzohydrazide (2b)

Mass (m/z): Calculated M.W: 152.15, Observed M.W: 153.42 (M+1)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO -d₆): δ = 10.61(Ar-OH, s, 1H), 9.5(-NH, s, 1H), 4.48(-NH₂, S, 1H), Ar(C-H) = 7.398(m, 2H), 7.33-7.5(d, 1H), 7.401-7.419(d, 1H)

Spectral details of 1-(2-bromobenzoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide(3a)

Mass (m/z): Calculated M.W: 350.0, Observed M.W: 352.8 (M+3)- Figure 1

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO -d₆): δ = 9.8(-NH, s, 1H), 9.60(-NH, s, 1H), 5.48(-NH, s, 1H), Ar(C-H) = 7.16(m, 1H), 7.566(m, 1H), 7.580(m, 2H), 7.599-7.602(d, 2H), 7.646(m, 1H), 7.652-7.655(d, 1H), 7.860-7.863(d, 1H). - Figure 2

Spectral details of 1-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide(3b)

Mass (m/z): Calculated M.W: 287.3, Observed M.W: 289.0 (M+1) - Figure 3

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO -d₆): δ = 11.87(-NH, s, 1H), 9.877(-NH, s, 1H), 3.32(-NH, s, 1H), 10.61(Ar-OH, s, 1H) Ar(C-H) = 6.96(m, 1H), 6.91-6.94(d, 2H), 7.13-7.16(d, 1H), 7.31-7.34(d, 1H), 7.44(m, 3H), 7.88(m, 2H). - Figure 4

Spectral details of 5-(2-bromophenyl)-N-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine (4a)

Mass (m/z): Calculated M.W: 316.0, Observed M.W: 319.0 (M+3) - Figure 5

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO -d₆): δ = 3.43(-NH, s, 1H), Ar(C-H) = 7.35(m, 4H), 7.5(m, 4H), 7.84-7.86(d, 1H). - Figure 6

Figure 1: Mass spectrum of 1-(2-bromobenzoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (3a)

Figure 2: ¹H NMR spectrum of 1-(2-bromobenzoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (3a)

Figure 3: Mass spectrum of 1-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (3b)

Figure 4: ¹H NMR spectrum of 1-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (3b)

Figure 5: Mass spectrum 5-(2-bromophenyl)-N-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine (4a)

Figure 6: ¹H NMR spectrum of 5-(2-bromophenyl)-N-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine (4a)

Figure (1-6) revealed the Mass spectra and ¹H NMR of compounds 3a-b, 4a respectively. Figure 1 and 3 of mass spectrum shows the existence of compounds 3a and 3b. The concerned mass of the compound 4a is in good agreement with the observed (319.0 m/z) and calculated value (316.0 m/z) were shown in figure (3). Proton NMR strongly empowered for the formation of the product by its δ value of compounds 3a, 3b and 4a. The δ value of compounds 3a, 3b and 4a are (δ = 9.8, 9.60, 5.48, 7.16, 7.566, 7.580, 7.599-7.602, 7.646, 7.652-7.655, 7.860-7.863), (δ = 11.87, 9.877, 3.32, 10.61, 6.96, 6.91-6.94, 7.13-7.16), 7.31-7.34, 7.44, 7.88) and (δ = 3.43, 7.35, 7.5, 7.84-7.86) ppm corresponding to the various -NH-, -OH, Ar-H protons were mentioned in Figure (2,4,6).

4. Conclusion:

In the present work substituted 5-(2-bromophenyl)-N-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine (4a) were synthesized successfully from the condensation of compounds (3a), (3b) in the presence of iodoacetic acid. Most of the researcher have been synthesized 1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine derivatives by using hazardous catalyst like thiosemicarbazide, one-pot from isoselenocyanates, using polymer-supported reagents, phosphonium mediated reagents, hypervalent Iodine mediated method. Etc., Which involves long time reaction and significant challenges during purification of the products, we have been synthesized the 1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine derivatives considerably simplified method used by iodoacetic acid as a cyclodesulfurization agent and using ethanol as solvent to provide desired product at 65°C, 3 hours without formation of side product with high yield. The chemical structures of compound (4a) have been confirmed using spectral techniques viz. Mass and ¹H-NMR were found to be in agreement with the chemical structures expected.

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